

An Energy-efficient Knowledge-based Smart Fan System Using Analytic Hierarchy Process and Fuzzy Logic

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Abstract: Electric fans have a big contribution to the electricity consumption of families in most of the highly populated regions of the world with hot and humid climates. Furthermore, with increasing the number of middle-income families, comfortability is becoming a significant factor in choosing electric fans. A smart fan can reduce electricity bills due to its high efficiency and create a personal comfort zone for the users due to its intelligent processing system. This paper proposes an automatic knowledge-based smart fan system that uses the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) and a fuzzy inference system for performing the intelligent operations. The system is equipped with appropriate sensors to acquire ambient temperature, gas, and light data. The AHP component and fuzzy inference system determine the speed of the fan efficiently and intelligently. The simulation results verify that the energy consumption of the smart system is nearly 35% less than that of the non-smart system. In addition, comparisons with some other existing fan systems show the energy efficiency of the proposed fan system. The prototype of the proposed system is built to observe the simulation performance and effectiveness via experiments.

Keywords: analytic hierarchy process (AHP); automatic fan system; energy-efficient; fuzzy inference system; knowledge-based system

1 Introduction

Efficient domestic energy consumption is a desire with short-terms gains (e.g., reduced energy bills) and long-term sustainability goals (e.g., reduced carbon footprint at large). According to the International Energy Agency (IEA), air conditioners and electric fans' contribution to electricity consumption is nearly 20% throughout the world that is expected to triple by 2050 [1]. Reports state this contribution is nearly 60% in Persian Gulf countries today [2]. With the progress in smart technology, the household users have access to the market of smart electric fans that simultaneously improve the user's experience of comfortability and reduce the total electricity consumption. Apart from domestic usages, electric

fans are an essential part of the cooling system in automobiles, PCs, modern refrigerators, etc, where the smartness can prolong the length of the fan's lifetime. A smart fan can acquire the environmental phenomena data (e.g., temperature, gas, and light data) via a set of sensors to accomplish its tasks efficiently. In the case of household electric fans, an intelligent and knowledge-based control unit additionally can take care of extra factors, such as user comfortability and preferences.

The basic model of a smart cooling fan has been introduced in [3] for the engine cooling system in automobiles. The engine coolant temperature is predicted using a simple mechanism based on available information of the vehicle, such as engine and vehicle speed, fuel, air temperature, etc. As a part of a smart thermal management control system development, automobile engine radiator fan(s) has been investigated in [4] for varying operation speed to heat rejection.

An automatic switching speed electric fan is designed and prototyped in [5]. The fan is programmed via a microcontroller to switch the speed according to temperature changes in the environment. The main controller of the system is a single-chip MC68HC11 that processes the input from a temperature sensor and tunes a DC motor's speed accordingly as its output. A smart electric fan model is proposed in [6] that uses the room temperature for speed control. An automatic on/off mechanism is suggested for the fan that performs based on the detection of users in its proximity via ultrasonic sensors. A smartphone-based app is developed in [7] to control the speed of a fan using the Wi-Fi connection. The speed of the fan can be regulated by the user through the app from 0% (stand still) to 100% (full speed). In [8], a human tracker fan is designed that controls the speed according to the temperature of the environment and rotates the fan toward the tracked user in the room via dual-element Pyroelectric Infrared Sensors (PIR). In [9], the fan is equipped with the temperature and PIR motion sensors connected to a microcontroller for processing signals from the sensor modules to adjust the fan's speed, its oscillation angle, and turning on/off. The motion detection module triggers the temperature sensing and objects location modules in the presence of people. Then, the microcontroller processes the signals transmitted from the modules to make the proper decisions. In [10], an IR remote fan speed control system, with the aim of eliminating human intervention to change the speed, has been designed and tested. The prototype model was implemented using ATmega328 on an Arduino Uno microcontroller board.

In [27], an automated fan system is presented that regulates the fan using a wireless sensor network in a plant factory. The system is composed of temperature, humidity, and illumination sensors as well as a gateway via an Ethernet communication protocol. Every time the environmental data are collected, the gateway estimates the heat locations at the cultivation shelf. Sensor nodes turn on the fan based on the pulse-width modulation (PWM) signals from the microcontroller. In [28], a smart fan platform is presented with a human tracking module to convert the living room into a smart environment. The

ultrasonic sensors detect the human position, and temperature sensors are used to adjust the fan speed. As it is seen, the aforementioned previous works focus on the automatization of fans rather than making them smart/smarter. Although many advantages smart fan systems have, very few research works have been done in this area.

Fuzzy logic is a knowledge-based system that can be used to improve the performance of engineering and control systems [35], [36]. It uses human experiences through the process of an intelligent inference to predict future state under complex and unpredictable conditions. Compared to other logics and also to some of the artificial intelligence techniques (e.g., deep learning), fuzzy logic is easy to implement. It has been widely used in embedded systems with low power-processing microcontrollers and with modern devices with high processing capacity [29], [30], [31], [32], [33], [34]. Fuzzy systems evaluate the current situation using fuzzy sets and linguistic terms (e.g., ‘cold’ and ‘cool’ for temperature) [18], [19]. Fuzzy inference system is a knowledge-based decision-making system that is composed of four main parts: fuzzification, rule base, inference engine, and defuzzification. The motivation of this work is missing a prototype-based study of knowledge-based and/or fuzzy-based smart electric fans for house conditions in the literature.

The user's comfort factors can be weighted according to their importance to the user via some techniques. These weighted factors can be then considered in the fuzzy decision-making system for efficiency together with the user's comfortability. AHP is a multi-criteria decision-making method that performs the relative pair-wise comparisons of several factors and options. It is used in various applications such as prioritizing, estimating costs, etc [14]-[17].

In this paper, an automatic knowledge-based smart fan system is proposed that is more energy-efficient and, at the same time, takes the user's preferences and experiences into account. The system uses an AHP component and a weighted fuzzy inference system to adjust the speed of the fan efficiently and intelligently. First, the AHP component assigns a set of weights to the sensory input data. Then, a fuzzy inference system determines the speed of the fan properly based on the weighted data received from the AHP component. The system is automatic, knowledge-based, and intelligent, as it uses user experiences in its decision-making processes in the AHP component and the fuzzy inference system. Consequently, the proposed smart fan simultaneously reduces energy consumption and improves user comfortability. A prototype of the proposed system is built for use in a living room, an office, or small indoor gardens.

The main contributions of the paper can be highlighted as:

- Knowledge-based automatic speed adjustment of an electric fan system based on phenomena data (e.g., temperature, gas, and light data)
- Using the AHP method to calculate the effective weights of each sensor based on its importance (for the user's comfort)

- Efficient decision making using a fuzzy inference system based on the user's experiences

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. The workflow of the proposed system, its components, and decision-making strategies are described in Section 2. The simulation study is carried out in Section 3. The design and prototype of the system are presented in Section 4. The paper is concluded in Section 5.

2 The Proposed Smart Fan System

The proposed smart electric fan system is composed of the input, process, and output units, as shown in Figure 1. The input unit contains DS18B20, MQ-9, and photocell sensors [11]-[13] to acquire environmental temperature, gas, and light, respectively. The processing unit is an ATmega16A microcontroller for processing the suggested AHP method and the proposed fuzzy inference system to adjust the speed of the fan. The output unit involves a DC motor and a 16×2 liquid-crystal display (LCD). The DC motor causes the fan blades rotation and the LCD shows the percentage of the motor's speed.

Figure 1

The components of the proposed smart fan system

Various sensors can be used in the design and implementation of smart fan systems. The temperature, gas, and light sensors are commonly used to reflect the actual environmental conditions. The ambient temperature is the most important parameter for designing a smart fan. The gas is an essential parameter in critical situations (e.g., fires and gas leaks). The light can be considered as a suitable parameter in fan systems to improve the comfortability of the user. We use these parameters simultaneously to adjust the fan's speed through an intelligent procedure.

The flowchart of the smart fan system is shown in Figure 2. The temperature (T), gas (G), and light (L) phenomena data are collected using the sensors and

transferred to the microcontroller. Afterwards, the AHP component calculates the weighted input by multiplying the sensor's inputs to their corresponding 'importance' weights as:

$$T_w = w_1 T, G_w = w_2 G, L_w = w_3 L \quad (1)$$

where T_w , G_w , and L_w are the weighted temperature, gas, and light, respectively, and w_1 , w_2 , and w_3 are their corresponding 'importance' weights ($w_1 + w_2 + w_3 = 1$). It is worth noting that we have used the MQ-9 sensor to detect various gases, especially carbon monoxide, methane, and liquefied petroleum gas (LPG), in the environment.

The fuzzy inference system calculates the speed of the DC motor according to the weighted input and the rule base. The LCD shows the percentage of the speed calculated as:

$$S_p = \frac{S}{S_{\max}} \times 100 \quad (2)$$

where S is the current speed of the DC motor and S_{\max} is its maximum speed. We define $S_{\max} = 255$ PWM. If $S_p < 10$ then the DC motor stops completely, and if $S_p > 80$ then it works at its highest speed. The speed of the DC motor is controlled by the microcontroller via the PWM timer. An 8-bit microcontroller processes the voltage supplies to the DC motor. Therefore, the speed is considered in the range of 0 to 255.

2.1 The AHP Method

The main element in AHP is a priority vector that is defined as:

$$W = [w_1, w_2, \dots, w_n], \sum w_i = 1 \quad (3)$$

The proposed AHP component uses three parameters including 'temperature importance', 'gas importance' and 'light importance' to determine their corresponding weights by the pair-wise comparisons. One scenario is represented in Table 1. The household user's preferences can lead to different scenarios. The table is read from right to left or vice versa depending on which half the symbol \surd is placed. For example, from Table 1, we can observe that 'temperature importance is equal to gas importance' or 'gas importance is strongly higher than light importance'.

Figure 2
The workflow of the proposed smart fan system

Table 1
Pair-wise comparison of the three parameters of the AHP component.

Importance	Relative scale (numerical scale)							Importance
	Extremely higher (9)	Strongly higher (6)	Slightly higher (3)	Equal (1)	Slightly higher (3)	Strongly higher (6)	Extremely higher (9)	
Temp (w_1)				√				Gas (w_2)
Temp (w_1)			√					Light (w_3)
Gas (w_2)		√						Light (w_3)

The magnitudes here demonstrate the so-called benefit index or more specifically, the user's comfort index. An alternative approach is to use the magnitudes to reflect the costs, the so-called cost index. The main objective of using the AHP component in this research is to evaluate and calculate the relative importance of the temperature, gas, and light parameters (as the parameters defining the user's comfort) to be used in the decision-making process.

The reciprocal matrix (on the left of (4)) shows the pair-wise comparison results of Table 1. Notice that, the lower triangular elements are reciprocal of the upper diagonal elements and all the elements are positive. Afterward, each element is divided by the sum of its column to get the normalized reciprocal matrix (on the right of (4)).

$$\begin{matrix} w_1 & w_2 & w_3 \\ w_1 & \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 & 3 \\ 1 & 1 & 6 \\ 1/3 & 1/6 & 1 \end{bmatrix} & \begin{bmatrix} 3/7 & 6/13 & 3/10 \\ 3/7 & 6/13 & 3/5 \\ 1/7 & 1/13 & 1/10 \end{bmatrix} \end{matrix}, \quad (4)$$

Finally, by calculating the average across the rows, the relative importance weights are obtained as:

$$\begin{bmatrix} w_1 \\ w_2 \\ w_3 \end{bmatrix} = \frac{1}{3} \times \begin{bmatrix} 3/7 + 6/13 + 3/10 \\ 3/7 + 6/13 + 3/5 \\ 1/7 + 1/13 + 1/10 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0.3967 \\ 0.4967 \\ 0.1066 \end{bmatrix} \cong \begin{bmatrix} 0.4 \\ 0.5 \\ 0.1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

From (5), it is seen that the importance weights of temperature and gas are greater than the importance of light. Therefore, the regulation of the fan speed is largely influenced by the variation of temperature and gas. Moreover, the speed regulation relies on a group of sensors, and in the case of a non-functioning sensor, the speed will be regulated appropriately. For the scenario represented in Table 1, we see that the gas input has the most and the light has the least importance in the decision-making process. The AHP component calculates these weights by using Algorithm 1. The vector of the importance weights is also known as the priority vector.

Algorithm 1 Calculation of the weights in the AHP component

```
n ← 3 /* number of decision variables*/
M[n][n] ← get from user /* pair-wise comparison matrix*/
S[n] ← 0 /* vector to save the sum of the columns in M*/
W[n] ← 0 /* importance weights vector*/
T ← 0
For i ← 1 to n
  For j ← 1 to n
    S[i] ← S[i] + M[i][j]
  End For
End For
For i ← 1 to n
  For j ← 1 to n
    M[i][j] ← M[i][j] / S[i]
  End For
End For
For i ← 1 to n
  For j ← 1 to n
    T ← T + M[i][j]
  End For
  W[i] ← T / n
  T ← 0
End For
Return W
```

2.2 The Fuzzy Inference System

The fuzzy inference system of the smart fan determines the speed of the DC motor. The weighted sensory data ‘temperature’, ‘gas’ and ‘light’ (i.e., T_w , G_w , and L_w , respectively), compose the fuzzy system inputs, and its output S is interpreted as the ‘speed’ of the DC motor. The universe sets of the inputs and output parameters are defined based on the physical specifications of the sensors and the DC motor. Fuzzy sets of the input parameters are determined by the triangular membership function [20] as:

$$F_{tr}(x; a, b, m) = \begin{cases} 0 & x \leq a \\ \frac{x-a}{m-a} & a < x \leq m \\ \frac{b-x}{b-m} & m < x < b \\ 0 & x \geq b \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

where x belongs to the universe of discourse, a is the lower limit, b is the upper limit, and m is the center of the triangle ($a < m < b$).

The output fuzzy parameter is determined with the bell-shaped membership function [21] as:

$$F_{be}(x; a, b, m) = \frac{1}{1 + \left(\frac{x - c}{a}\right)^{2b}} \quad (7)$$

where x represents an element of the universe of discourse, a and c are applied to regulate the width and center of the membership function, and b is the slope at the cross points. The universe set of the input parameters and associated linguistic terms are given in Table 2. The universes of the discourse of the inputs and the output are determined based on the detection range of the sensors and the working range of the DC motor.

Table 2
The universe sets and associated linguistic terms of the fuzzy inference system.

Fuzzy variable	Unit	Universe set	Linguistic terms
Temp.	°C	{-55, 0, 30, 80, 125}	{‘Cold’, ‘Moderate’, ‘Warm’, ‘Hot’}
Gas (Density)	ppm	{10, 2500, 5000, 7500, 10000}	{‘Low’, ‘Normal’, ‘High’, ‘Extreme’}
Light	lx	{0, 32500, 65000, 97500, 130000}	{‘Dark’, ‘Standard’, ‘Bright’, ‘Very Bright’}
Speed	PWM	{0, 50, 127, 200, 255}	{‘Low’, ‘Medium’, ‘High’, ‘Very High’}

Table 3 represents the fuzzy rules of the fuzzy inference system. There are 32 fuzzy rules considered in the system. As it is seen from the table, the inputs and output are in direct proportion. That is, if the inputs are low then the speed is relatively low, and if the inputs are high then the speed is relatively high.

Table 3
Fuzzy rules of the proposed fuzzy inference system.

Rule no.	Antecedents			Consequent	Rule no.	Antecedents			Consequent
	Temp.	Gas	Light	Speed		Temp.	Gas	Light	Speed
1	Cold	Low	Dark	Low	17	Warm	Low	Dark	Low
2	Cold	Low	Standard	Low	18	Warm	Low	Standard	Low
3	Cold	Normal	Bright	Low	19	Warm	Normal	Bright	Medium
4	Cold	Normal	Very Bright	Low	20	Warm	Normal	Very Bright	Medium
5	Cold	High	Dark	Medium	21	Warm	High	Dark	High
6	Cold	High	Standard	Medium	22	Warm	High	Standard	Very High
7	Cold	Extreme	Bright	High	23	Warm	Extreme	Bright	Very High
8	Cold	Extreme	Very	High	24	Warm	Extreme	Very	Very High

			Bright					Bright	
9	Moderate	Low	Dark	Low	25	Hot	Low	Dark	Medium
10	Moderate	Low	Standard	Low	26	Hot	Low	Standard	Medium
11	Moderate	Normal	Bright	Low	27	Hot	Normal	Bright	High
12	Moderate	Normal	Very Bright	Medium	28	Hot	Normal	Very Bright	High
13	Moderate	High	Dark	Medium	29	Hot	High	Dark	Very High
14	Moderate	High	Standard	High	30	Hot	High	Standard	Very High
15	Moderate	Extreme	Bright	High	31	Hot	Extreme	Bright	Very High
16	Moderate	Extreme	Very Bright	Very High	32	Hot	Extreme	Very Bright	Very High

The fuzzy control rules of the inference system are specified by the Mamdani model [22] in the form of:

Rule i : if x is A_i and y is B_i and z is C_i then o is S_i

where A_i , B_i , C_i , and S_i denote the fuzzy sets, x , y , and z are the inputs, and o is the output. Each fuzzy rule can be represented via a rule matrix. Consider Rule i from Table 3 and let, $A_i = (a_{i1}, \dots, a_{i5})$, $B_i = (b_{i1}, \dots, b_{i5})$, $C_i = (c_{i1}, \dots, c_{i5})$, and $S_i = (s_{i1}, \dots, s_{i5})$. Define

$$K_i = A_i \wedge B_i \wedge C_i = \min \{ a_{ij}, b_{ij}, c_{ij} \} = (k_{i1}, \dots, k_{i5}) \quad (8)$$

$$L_i = A_i \vee B_i \vee C_i = \max \{ a_{ij}, b_{ij}, c_{ij} \} = (l_{i1}, \dots, l_{i5}) \quad (9)$$

Then, the fuzzy rule matrices of Rule i (R_i) and the fuzzy inference system are defined as:

$$R_i = \begin{bmatrix} \min \{ k_{i1}, s_{i1} \} & \cdots & \min \{ k_{i1}, s_{i4} \} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \min \{ k_{i4}, s_{i1} \} & \cdots & \min \{ k_{i4}, s_{i4} \} \end{bmatrix}, \quad R = R_1 \vee R_2 \vee \cdots \vee R_{32} \quad (10)$$

The fuzzy inference engine uses the max-min composition to determine the speed of the DC motor through the following inference process

$$F_s = \{A_i, B_i, C_i\} \circ R = \max \{ \min \{ \{A_i, B_i, C_i\} \circ R \} \} \quad (11)$$

By a defuzzification procedure, the inferred fuzzy result is converted to a non-fuzzy crisp value that summarizes the fuzzy set. For n rules in the rule matrix, the crisp control (i.e., the speed) is derived by the weighted average defuzzification method that is the most frequently used because of its computation efficiency [23]:

$$u_i = \frac{\sum_j F_{be}(x_i) [F_s]_{ij}}{\sum_j F_{be}(x_i)} \quad (12)$$

where u_i is defuzzified output for Rule i and $F_{be}(\cdot)$ is the degree of output membership function (from Table 2) for the speed. Figure 3 shows the proposed fuzzy inference system.

Figure 3
The proposed fuzzy inference system

3 Simulations

3.1 Verification

In this section, the effectiveness of the proposed smart fan system is demonstrated through the simulation results. The prototype of the system is discussed in the next section. Current and energy consumption are two important characteristics of DC motors [24]-[26]. Figure 4 illustrates sensory input data versus the speed, current, and energy consumption of the DC motor over 10 hours of simulation data with the sampling period of 1 minute. It is seen that a non-smart fan system's energy consumption is growing fast in comparison with the smart system over the time interval. The speed is determined by the AHP component and the fuzzy inference system. The simulation results indicate that the speed is suitably adapted to the changes in sensory (input) data. The proposed system determines PWM appropriately to adjust the voltage supplied to the DC motor, so the speed is

regulated based on environmental conditions, and therefore, energy efficiency is achieved.

The total energy consumptions of the non-smart and smart systems are calculated as:

$$T_{E1} = I.VO.t, \quad T_{E2} = I.VO.t \cdot \frac{S}{S_{\max}} \quad (13)$$

where T_{E1} (W) and T_{E2} (W) denote the total energy consumption of the non-smart and smart systems, respectively, I is the current (mA), VO (V) is the voltage of the DC motor, t (min) is time, S is the current speed of the DC motor, and S_{\max} is its maximum speed. The simulation results are obtained with assuming $I = 500$ mA, $S_{\max} = 255$ PWM, and $VO = 6$ V. From (13), it is seen that the smart system is energy efficient.

Figure 5 shows the variation of the speed versus the variation of one of the sensory inputs while the other two parameters are kept constant. The default values for the constant sensory inputs are set to 40°C, 5000 ppm (parts per million), and 45000 lx, for temperature, gas, and light, respectively. It is seen that the temperature and speed of the DC motor are in direct proportion, so the temperature is increased when the speed increases. The speed increases to decrease the ambient temperature. From the figure, we do not observe an explicit relation between changing the level of gas and the speed of the DC motor. Finally, we observe that changing the level of light causes the speed of the DC to be unstable after a while. However, as the level of light goes higher, the speed converges to stability and a constant point.

Figure 6 shows the sensory data from the temperature, gas, and light sensors, and DC motor's speed, where one of the sensors is not functioning normally due to the phenomenon situations (e.g., fire and end of life). In Figure 6(a), the temperature sensor is malfunctioning, so the temperature data is equal to -55°C. In Figure 6(b), the gas sensor is malfunctioning, so the gas data is equal to 10 ppm. In addition, in Figure 6(c), the light sensor is malfunctioning, so the light data is equal to 0 lx. From the results of the simulation, it can be seen that the proposed system can work efficiently in determining the motor's speed based on data from the normal functioning sensors while one of the sensors is malfunctioning. This feature indicates that the fan system is robust and efficient to the sensor malfunctioning.

Figure 4

From the top-left, sensory data from the temperature, gas, and light sensors, DC motor's speed, and energy consumption

Figure 5

From the top, the impact of the change in the level of temperature, gas, and light sensory data on the DC motor's speed

Figure 6

Sensory data and the DC motor's speed when (a) the temperature, (b) the gas, and (c) the light sensor is malfunctioning

To maintain the user's comfortability, stability is one of the most important requirements to consider in fan systems. The fan speed should be adjusted moderately and the sharp changes in the speed must be avoided. Since the proposed smart fan system uses a multi-criteria decision-making method, the fan speed does not increase/decrease suddenly even when one of the sensory inputs changes sharply. The simulation results in figures 4-6 indicate that the proposed system adjusts the fan speed efficiently while the stability is preserved.

3.2 Comparison

Table 4 compares the proposed smart fan with the state-of-the-art prototypes. As it is seen from the table, our proposed smart fan uses more environmental parameters compared to other systems, and it makes an intelligent decision based on a knowledge-based inference system while the other systems are mostly programmed for predefined simple scenarios.

Table 4

The proposed smart fan system versus state-of-the-art

<i>Reference</i>	<i>Sensor type</i>	<i>Automatic</i>	<i>Knowledge-based</i>	<i>Intelligent decision-making</i>
[3]	Temp.	√	×	×
[5]	Temp.	√	×	×
[27]	Temp., Humidity,	√	×	×

	Illumination			
[28]	Temp., Ultrasonic,	√	×	×
[9]	Temp., Infrared, Ultrasonic	√	×	×
This work	Temperature, Gas, Light	√	√	√

We also evaluated the performance of the proposed system in terms of speed and energy consumption in comparison with some of the existing works (see Figure 7). The evaluation results demonstrate that the proposed system regulates the speed of the fan based on phenomena data properly and as a result, the energy consumption is decreased considerably. It is worth noting that the methods presented in [9], [28] turn off the fan when the temperature is less than 25°C and the approach presented in [27] turns off the fan when the temperature is less than 25°C and the illumination is less than 50000 lx.

Figure 7

Comparison results. (a) the proposed system, (b) the methods presented in [9], [28], and (c) the approach presented in [27]

4 Design and Implementation

The proposed fan system is designed in Proteus Pro 8.4 platform (see Figure 8). The microcontroller is coded in CodeVison AVR 3.12. One crystal and two capacitors are used to handle the external interrupt of the microcontroller. The digital temperature sensor DS18B20 is connected to the microcontroller. The percentage of the DC motor's speed is shown on the LCD which is controlled through port B. The DC motor is regulated by the microcontroller via its port D with the aid of motor driver L293D. On the LCD, the displayed info T , G , L , and S indicate the temperature, gas, light, and the speed of the fan system, respectively. Note that if the speed is less than 10%, the fan will stop, but if the speed is greater than 80%, the fan will run at the highest speed.

The DS18B20, MQ-9, and photocell sensors are utilized to sense the ambient temperature, gas, and light. The DC motor is supplied with the maximum voltage of 6V as well as the speed of the DC motor is adjusted every 1 min. The power of

the circuit is supplied by an AC 220V to DC 6V adaptor. The system is turned on by the power button and can be reset by the reset button. The speed percentage is shown on a 16×2 LCD based on sensory input data and the proposed strategies. In [37], the parameters of the DC motor are described. Besides, Table 5 provides the parameters and their default values that are used in the simulations, (circuit) design, and implementation.

Figure 8

The circuit design of the proposed smart fan system

Table 5

Simulation, design, and implementation parameters

<i>Parameter</i>	<i>Default value</i>
Simulation time	10 h
Temperature value	40°C
Gas value	5000 ppm
Light value	45000 lx
Voltage of the DC motor	6V

Sampling period of the DC motor	1 min
Current	500 mA
S_{max}	255 PWM

5 Conclusion and Future Work

This paper has proposed an automatic knowledge-based smart fan system for intelligent energy consumption and enhancing the user's comfortability and experience. The system uses an AHP component and a weighted fuzzy inference system to determine the speed of the fan according to the sensed ambient temperature, gas, and light. The performance of the system has been evaluated in comparison with the non-smart and several existing models. It is shown that the proposed smart system reaches the significant achievements in terms of energy-efficiency. In the future works, humidity sensors will be added to the system to improve the user's comfortability and experience. Moreover, deep neural network (DNN) can be integrated into the intelligent controller to enhance the performance of the system.

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